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Transport, utilization and storage of CO₂ emissions produced by cement industry: CCUS study of the CLEANKER project

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Abstract

The EU Horizon 2020 project CLEANKER is aimed on Ca-looping capture of CO₂ emissions produced by cement industry. For the first time capture-focused EU project includes the full CCUS value chain study. This study includes techno-economic modelling of CO₂ transport, storage, and utilization scenarios; CCUS regulatory issues; definition of BUZZI and ITC-HCG cement plants suitable for first-of-a-kind CCS plant based on transport and storage opportunities; mineral trapping of CO₂ from the demo system and testing the carbonated materials for reuse in concrete.

Gaps in national regulations were analysed for Italy, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Russia involved in two planned CCUS scenarios (Italian and Baltic). Russia is one of the largest emitters and Estonia has one of the highest CO₂ emissions per capita in the world. Russia has not ratified yet Paris Climate Agreement. Latvia, Lithuania and Russia are not parties of the London Protocol. CO₂ use options in these countries include CO₂ use for EOR, Geothermal Energy Recovery and mineral carbonation using waste materials. Additional CCUS regulations and political incentives are needed in these countries. Estonian burnt oil shale could be used as an effective sorbent in the proposed CO₂-mineralization process, binding up to 0.18 kg CO₂ per kg of waste. The onshore CCUS scenario was proposed for CO₂ emissions produced and captured by Kunda Nordic Cement plant (KNC), Eesti and Balti power plants, and Latvenergo TEC-2, the largest CO₂ emitters in Estonia and Latvia. CCUS scenario includes mineral carbonation of 1.2 mln tonnes CO₂ and transport and storage of about 10 mln tonnes annually into North-Blidene and Blidene structures in the western Latvia. The average optimistic capacity of the structures (297 Mt CO₂) will allow to store these emissions for at least 29.5 years. The share of the Estonian emissions stored in Latvia will be about 92.6%, including 5.6% by KNC. Latvian stored emissions will compose 7.4%. Such scenario will support Estonia and Latvia to reach their climate strategic targets. Techno-economic modelling of this scenario will be the next step of this study. Utilizing of the re-carbonated wastes in concrete application supports closing the CO₂ cycle of Vernasca cement plant by trapping the carbon dioxide into a concrete that contains the cement of the same plant.

Keywords: CO₂ emissions; Cement plant, CCUS regulations; CO₂ mineral carbonation; oil shale ash; CCUS scenario; CO₂ storage

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1. Introduction

The main objectives of CCUS study is to explore local and regional transport, utilization and storage needs, options and solutions in the vicinity of the Vernasca cement plant in Italy, the Kunda cement plant in Estonia and Slantsy cement plant in Russia. Integration of the local and regional transport networks, infrastructure and synergy with other large CO₂ emission sources were planned by modelling of one local and one regional CCUS scenarios.

In the present paper one possible Estonian-Latvian transboundary CCUS scenario is proposed for further development and modelling. Italian local scenario, which can include CO₂ use for EOR and Geothermal Energy Recovery and storage in depleted oil fields and saline aquifers in Lombardy Region, will be developed later. Such scenarios are the first step towards creation of national and regional CCUS networks and infrastructure involving cement plants operated by the end-users of the project.

Nomenclature

BOS	burnt oil shale
CDW	concrete demolition waste
CCUS	Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage
EOR	Enhanced Oil Recovery
EU ETS	European Union Emission Trading System
EU28	European Union 28 Member States
GER	Geothermal Energy Recovery
HCG	Heidelberg Cement Group
KNC	Kunda Nordic Cement Plant
PF	pulverised firing

2. Samples and experimental methods

Solid wastes from power and cement sectors were utilized to produce aggregates for construction industry by carbonation-based solidification technique. BOS1, BOS3 and BOS7 are ashes from electrostatic precipitators and BOS2, BOS4 and BOS8 are ashes from total ash silo of circulating fluidized bed boilers of Eesti, Balti and Auvere power plants, respectively. The PF ash sample BOS5 is from SO₂ removal system (Novel Integrated Desulphurization, Alstom Power). BOS6 is from Enefit280 units that produce shale oil. Two different suppliers of concrete demolition wastes (CDW) provided samples: I.L.C. s.r.l (Rondissone, TO) and Isoltrasporti (Isola Sant'Antonio, AL). Each of them delivered fine fractions of two different materials: recycled demolition waste (CDW1 and CDW3) and demolition waste selectively derived from concrete (CDW2) and recycled demolition waste submitted to washing process (CDW4). The materials were analyzed using quantitative X-ray diffraction (Bruker D8 Advanced) and chemical analysis for determining the contents of free lime (ethylene glycol method [1]) and total carbon (Electra CS - 580 Carbon/ Sulfur Determinator).

The experiments were carried out in a semi-batch Eirich EL1 type intensive mixer (Fig. 1). The wastes were treated under different operating regimes (by varying rotation speed from 300 to 3000 rpm, CO₂ content in model gas from 20 to 70%, gas flow from 30 to 400 L/h and the mass of initial sample from 150 to 600 g). The CO₂ content in gas phase was detected by Doutec infrared analyzer and the carbonated samples were dried in thermostat for 3h at 105°C and analyzed for TC and free lime content as the main indicators for the carbonation process.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup

3. Industrial and Fossil CO₂ emissions

Global Fossil CO₂ emissions are for the third year in a row plateauing with no further increase to a total of 35.8 Gt CO₂ in 2016. The global CO₂ per capita emissions were 4.8 t/yr. The EU28 emissions mainly decreased over the past two decades reaching reduction levels in 2016 of 20.8% compared to 1990 and 17.9% compared to 2005. In 2016 the EU28 emitted 3.4 Gt CO₂, which corresponds to 6.75 t CO₂ emissions per capita (Janssens-Maenhout et al, 2017, EC JRC, 2018). However, in 2016 in the studied EU countries both total CO₂ emissions and CO₂ emissions per capita have increased compared to 2015 (Table 1). CO₂ emissions per capita were lower than world and EU averages only in Latvia and Lithuania, while in Italy CO₂ emissions per capita were higher than in the world. CO₂ emissions per capita were higher than the world and EU28 average in Russia and Estonia (Table 1). Estonian CO₂ emissions per capita were 3.5 times higher than in the world and 2.5 times higher than EU28 average. Estonian emissions per capita were at the second place in Europe (after Luxemburg) and at 11-12th place in the world [2].

Table 1. Fossil CO₂ Emissions [2, 3]

Country	CO ₂ total emissions (Mt/yr)			CO ₂ per capita emissions (t CO ₂ /cap/yr)		
	1990	2015	2016	1990	2015	2016
Italy	423.3	355.14	358.14	7.41	5.97	6.03
Estonia	36.97	22.18	22.40	23.55	16.8	17.1
Latvia	20.32	7.89	8.16	7.64	3.96	4.14
Lithuania	35.1	13.33	13.69	9.49	4.55	4.7
Russia	2379.4	1698	1662	16.08	11.79	11.54

The EU ETS now operates in 31 countries (the 28 EU Member States plus Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway). As of 2013 it covers CO₂ emissions from 11,000 power plants and manufacturing installations and slightly over 500 aircraft operators flying between EEA's airports. It covers around 45% of the EU's GHG emissions. As of Phase 3 (2013-2020), the sectors with stationary installations regulated by the EU ETS are energy intensive industries, including power stations and other combustion plants with >20 MW thermal rated input, CO₂ capture, transport in pipelines and geological storage of CO₂. National installations registered in 2015 in EU ETS produced 143635 kt of CO₂ in Italy, 10996, 1714 and 6028 kt of CO₂ in Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania correspondingly (Table 2).

Table 2. EU ETS national data in 2015 [4]

Country	Fuel consumption (TJ)	CO ₂ emissions (kt)	Number of registered installations				In total
			< 25 000 t CO ₂ -eq	25 000 - 50 000 t CO ₂ -eq	50 000 - 500 000 t CO ₂ -eq	>500 000 t CO ₂ -eq	
Italy	2078031	143635	-	744	234	93	1071
Estonia	106684	10996	28	5	8	4	45
Latvia	30173	1714	56	4	2	2	64
Lithuania	99940	6028	78	3	6	3	90

During 2015-2017 registered in EU ETS emissions did not decrease in Italy and significantly increased in Estonia (about 20% during 2016-2017), but they decreased in Latvia. In Lithuania 2014-2016 decrease stopped in 2017 (Table 1). Roughly 60% of Estonia's fuel balance is covered by oil shale with an annual mining output of 14–16 Mt. Its share in power production exceeds 95%. Electricity generation produces about 7 Mt of waste ash every year [5].

Table 3. CO₂ Emissions from industrial installations as a percentage of the previous year [6]

Country	2014	2015	2016	2017
Italy	92.78	102.24	99.22	100.16
Estonia	94.08	79.52	112.49	109.22
Latvia	89.67	101.03	95.78	94.87
Lithuania	91.41	99.79	90.32	101.92

Kunda Nordic Cement Plant (KNC) is located in the northern Estonia about 80-90 km west of the largest in the country Eesti and Balti power plants. The KNC is located in a small town of Kunda, currently HCG (Germany) has 75% and CRH (Ireland) 25% of the shares [7]. KNC produces constructional cements, crushed limestone and provides port services [8]. Nearly all cement consumption in Estonia is covered by the KNC [9]. KNC operates a wet cement production process. Its main energy source is oil shale. The main raw materials that it uses are clay, limestone and oil shale ash. Clay and limestone are mined in nearby quarries. Cement, or Portland cement, is made when limestone, clay (or sand), and fuel is burnt in a rotary kiln. During the burning process the material is forming a gravel-like, extremely hard-burned, clinker. The clinker is either used as such, or ground in cement mills together with small amounts of other material (plaster) to form the cement [7]. About 60% of CO₂ emissions from the cement production come from the calcining process, when the intermediate product clinker is produced. The remaining 40% of CO₂ emissions come from the combustion of fuels used to produce heat during the production process. KNC has formulated a zero vision for CO₂ emissions over the product's life cycle. Actions in five areas are required: energy efficiency, using biomass as energy, new cement types, carbon capture and storage and CO₂ mineral carbonation [10].

KNC has exported most of the clinker to Cesla cement plant in Slantsy (HCG). Due to the loss of Russian market, KNC had to reduce its clinker production by two times in 2015 compared to 2014. This also resulted in two times decrease of CO₂ emission in 2015. According to EU ETS the CO₂ emissions have increased for 69.7% in

2017, as a result of the increased production. This increase was the highest among the all Estonian large CO₂ emitters (Table 4).

Table 4. Key figures for KNC in 2013 – 2016 [11]

Production	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Clinker, t	691 443	720 480	356 287	318 500	NA
Cement, t	456 070	447 350	390 430	422 800	NA
Fuel					
Oil shale, t	155 750	150 120	70 201	48 313	NA
Coal, t	58 900	63 850	22 913	19 176	NA
Alternative fuels, t	71 600	78 740	51 640	51 558	NA
Emissions					
CO ₂ , t	748 123	785 695	379 310	331 299	559 629
Environmental investments, M €	0.98	0.49	0.91	1.89	NA

4. Gaps in international and national regulations

CO₂ storage, transport and utilization costs could depend on national and regional regulations. For example, CO₂ storage monitoring costs, which depends on the requirements for monitoring, should be included into the storage costs. Most of the EU countries implemented EU CCS Directive by 2013. CO₂ use options were not included into EU CCS Directive (2009), but some CO₂ use issues appeared in the Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines under the EU ETS Directive [12]. CCS laws should be applied together with four guidelines to CCS Directive, EU Emission Trading System (EU ETS) and its Monitoring and Reporting Guidelines.

International and national regulations related to CCUS technology and their national implementations are compared for five countries (Italy, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Russia) involved in the planned CCUS scenarios of the CLEANKER project. Among the studied countries only Russia has not ratified yet the Paris Climate Agreement. Latvia, Lithuania and Russia are not yet parties of the London Protocol. This prohibits the export of CO₂ from a contracting party to other countries for injection into subseabed geological formations. The protocol was amended in 2009 to enable cross-border CCS projects, but the amendment must be ratified by two-thirds of contracting parties to enter into force.

Russia is one of the largest emitters and Estonia has one of the highest CO₂ emissions per capita in the world. CO₂ emissions from the cement industry should be considered as at the second place after the energy sector and could be captured and stored within common CCUS scenarios. The climate strategic targets should be increased in all the studied countries to reach the Paris targets and CCUS technology should be included in the list of technological priorities together with renewables and energy storage in all the countries and in the Baltic Sea Region.

CO₂ use options in the studied countries including CO₂ use for EOR, GER, mineral carbonation using waste materials, should be considered in synergy with CO₂ storage in both Italian and Baltic Scenarios. Italy is one of the most prospective country for CO₂ use for EOR and GER among studied countries and in Europe. Additional CCUS regulations and political incentives are needed in all the studied countries. Specific CO₂ storage and emissions monitoring laws at the storage sites should be developed in Latvia and Russia. National, industrial and EU support are needed to start the first full CCUS projects in Italy, Baltic States and Russia. Educational and increasing public awareness activities supported by academic and research institutions and media support to explain benefits of climate change mitigation are needed for both scenarios and in the all studied countries.

5. Results on mineral carbonation

Experimental part of the study includes mineral trapping of CO₂ from the demo system. The laboratory tests on burnt oil shale and CDW carbonation were carried out in order to identify the most promising materials for CO₂ capture and to build a kinetic model for process upscale. The main objective of this task is the construction and

operation of a large (100 L to 1000L) device for mineralization of CO₂ from the Vernasca demonstration plant, using selected types of burnt oil shale and the CDW from different locations.

The phase composition indicated that the burnt oil shale samples (apart from BOS6) contained a considerable amount lime, portlandite and secondary Ca-silicates, which attribute as potential CO₂ binders (Fig 2a). In CDW samples supplied by I.L.C. (CDW1 and CDW2) quartz and silicates accounted for about 80% of the total mineral composition. Samples supplied by Isoltrasporti (CDW3 and CDW4) had much higher amount of carbonates against a lower content of silicates, while the quantity of quartz was similar.

Carbonation tests indicated that the free lime content was exhausted within 30 min in the conditions of low range water solid ratio (0.2 w/w) and gas flow of 70% CO₂ in air (Fig. 2b). The CO₂ uptake was mainly attributed by the free lime content, which is relatively high (10-15%) in burnt oil shale, but non-existent in concrete demolition wastes. Changing different parameters indicated that increasing sample mass and gas flow rate accelerated and intensified the carbonation process as changing the mixing speed from 300 to 3000 rpm had negligible effect. A kinetic model built on Ca(OH)₂ solubility [13] and carbonation [14] followed the experimental results for Ca(OH)₂ content during carbonation but underestimated the carbonate content in solid phase. This is due to Ca-silicates that also contribute to CO₂ binding but were not considered in this model.

Fig. 2. (a) The phase composition of initial samples and (b) carbonation results of BOS3 and BOS7 model vs experiment (process parameters: gas mixture 400 L/h, 70% CO₂, 600 g initial sample, rotation speed 300 rpm).

Based on the results, selected types of burnt oil shale could be used as effective sorbents in the proposed CO₂-mineralization process, binding up to 0.18 kg CO₂ per kg of waste. Theoretical annual binding ability of 7 Mt of Estonian oil shale ash is about 1.26 Mt CO₂. Utilizing re-carbonated wastes in concrete application supports closing the CO₂ cycle of Vernasca cement plant by trapping the carbon dioxide into a concrete that contains the cement of the same plant.

6. Estonian-Latvian onshore CCUS scenario

The North Blidene and Blidene structures, the largest prospective for CO₂ storage structures located in the western Latvia, were chosen for the Estonian-Latvian onshore CCUS scenario. Their storage capacity was estimated earlier as 74 and 58 Mt CO₂. The North Blidene is an anticlinal near-fault fold with three domes. The Blidene structure is located in a down-dip block. The Blidene structure is bounded by faults at the north-west and south-east. The structure is studied by five wells [15].

Fig. 3. (a) Contour maps and (b) 3D structure maps of the Deimena Formation in the North Blidene (above) and the Blidene (below) structures composed using Golden Software Surfer 15 software. Fault line is indicated with red polyline [11].

In the present study new contour and 3D structure maps were composed and CO₂ storage capacity of the Blidene and the North Blidene structures (Fig.3) were calculated using improved estimations of all needed parameters. Minimum, maximum and average capacities were estimated for optimistic and conservative cases for both structures (Table 5) using approach presented in [15]. Their total optimistic capacity (min-max/mean) is 186-380/297 Mt, while the conservative capacity was estimated as 33.6-68.0/53.4 Mt. The average optimistic capacity is more than two times higher than the capacity estimated in the previous reports (132 Mt) [15], explained by a larger estimated area and a higher CO₂ density in this study. The average conservative capacity in this study is lower by 2.5 times, explained by the lower storage efficiency applied [11].

Table 5. Physical parameters of the studied structural traps [11]

Structure	North Blidene	Blidene
Depth of reservoir top, m	1035-1150	1168-1357
Reservoir thickness, m	48	66
Trap area, km ²	141	62
CO ₂ density, kg/m ³	881	866
Net to gross ratio, %	75	80
Salinity, g/l	100-114	100-114
T, °C	18	22.9
Storage efficiency factor (S_{eff}) Optimistic/Conservative (%)	30/4	5/3
Porosity (min-max/avg), %	12.5-25.6/20	13.5-26.6/21
Optimistic CO ₂ storage capacity (min-max/avg), Mt	167-342/267	19-37.5/29.6
Conservative CO ₂ storage capacity (min-max/avg), Mt	22.2-45.5/35.6	11.4-22.5/17.8

Proposed Estonian-Latvian onshore CCUS scenario includes CO₂ emissions produced and captured by KNC, Eesti and Balti power plants (the largest industrial CO₂ emission sources in Estonia), and the largest CO₂ emitter in Latvia (Latvenergo, TEC-2) into both the North-Blidene and the Blidene structures (Fig.4). These four plants produced in 2017 together 11.26 Mt CO₂.

Fig. 4. Proposed Estonian-Latvian CCUS scenario, including three Estonian and one Latvian CO₂ producers

Considering that 1.2 Mt CO₂ could be utilized by mineral carbonation of oil shale ash, the total annual amount for storage will be only 10.06 Mt. The average optimistic capacity of the Blidene and the North Blidene structures (297 Mt CO₂) will allow for the storage of emissions produced by these four enterprises for at least 29.5 years (Table 6). This scenario will need drilling of eight injection boreholes and construction of about 800 km of CO₂ transport pipelines. The share of Estonian CO₂ emissions stored in this scenario will be about 92.6%, including 5.6% by KNC. Latvian emissions will compose 7.4% of the stored in the structures. Compared to the previously modeled Estonian-Latvian CCS scenario for the Balti and the Eesti power plants with their estimated 8 years of the project duration [16], this scenario has an advantage of including the cement industry and CO₂ mineral carbonation in Estonia and the power plant from Latvia with the probability of the project duration lasting for more than 29 years. This scenario will help Estonia and Latvia to reach their national strategic emission reduction targets.

Table 6. Planned parameters of Estonian-Latvian CCUS scenario

Technical parameters	Estonian plants				Total Estonian share	Latvian share	Estonian-Latvian CCUS
	KNC	Eesti	Balti	CO ₂ use			
Emissions sources	KNC	Eesti	Balti	CO ₂ use	3 plants	Latvenergo, TEC2	4 plants
CO ₂ emissions per year, Mt	0.56	8.36	1.6	-1.2	9.32	0.74	10.06
Total CO ₂ emissions during 29.5 years, Mt	16.5	246.6	47.2	-35.4	274.9	21.8	296.8
Total CO ₂ emissions during 29.5 years, %	5.57	83.10	15.90	-11.93	92.64	7.36	100
Number of wells	1	6		-	7	1	8
Transport, km	750	800	800	-	800	70	800
Pipeline diameter, mm	800	800	800	800	800	300	800

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